

Application of CUF for the Structural Optimization of Wings

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The aerospace sector increasingly demands efficient structural analysis methodologies to design lightweight, cost-effective, and sustainable aircraft while reducing development time. Although traditional global Finite Element Methods (FEMs) strike a balance between accuracy and numerical efficiency, their computational cost remains prohibitive, if large-scale optimisation tasks are required to design and size novel configurations, limiting their applicability in the early stages of design. This paper introduces a novel framework integrating Carrera's Unified Formulation (CUF) with gradient-based optimisation techniques to enable precise and computationally efficient structural designs for aerospace applications. By augmenting beam element-based Finite Element Methods (FEM) with CUF, the suggested methodology provides adaptable prediction accuracy while achieving substantial reductions in computational cost, compared to conventional global FEM approaches. The adjoint method, implemented through Automatic Differentiation (AD) in reverse mode, enables exact gradient computation, addressing the challenges of high-dimensional optimisation problems. Results demonstrate that CUF provides a robust alternative to conventional shell-based modelling, particularly for preliminary design phases, achieving comparable stress predictions while reducing computational time by up to 97%. This capability accelerates the development of more efficient and sustainable aircraft designs.

Nomenclature

$B4$	=	Beam elements with four nodes
C	=	Hooke's law stiffness matrix
F_τ, F_s	=	Expansion functions
L_{ext}	=	Virtual work of the external forces
L_{int}	=	Virtual work of internal forces
\mathbf{K}	=	Global stiffness matrix
\mathbf{P}	=	Global force vector
N_i, N_j	=	Shape functions (e.g., Lagrange polynomials)
$F_\tau(y, z)$	=	Cross-sectional shape functions
$\delta\mathcal{L}$	=	Virtual work (Lagrangian functional variation)
ν	=	Poisson's ratio
ρ	=	Material density
$\boldsymbol{\sigma}$	=	Stress vector
L	=	Length of the beam
t_p	=	Base panel thickness
t_w	=	Stringer web thickness

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t_f	=	Stringer flange thickness
TE	=	Taylor Expansion
MPI	=	Message Passing Interface
$DOFs$	=	Degrees of Freedom
$f(x, u)$	=	Objective function
$r(u; x)$	=	Governing equations residual
ψ	=	Adjoint variable
σ_i	=	Nodal stress at location i
σ_{ADM}	=	Allowable material stress
$KS(g(x))$	=	Kreisselmeier-Steinhauser constraint aggregation function
\mathbf{u}	=	Displacement vector
$\delta\mathbf{u}$	=	Virtual displacement vector
$k_{\tau s}^{ij}$	=	Fundamental nucleus of the stiffness matrix
x, y, z	=	Orthogonal Cartesian reference system
E	=	Young's modulus

I. Introduction

Structural analysis is essential for ensuring, integrity, safety, reliability, and efficiency of aircraft structures. This discipline underpins the design and certification of aerospace components, enabling precise predictions of airframe mechanical behaviour across a wide range of operative conditions.

Traditional beam-based methods, such as the Euler-Bernoulli Beam Theory (EBBT) and Timoshenko Beam Theory (TBT), have served as foundational analytical tools for simplifying the study of elongated structures like wings and fuselages. The EBBT offers insights into pure bending, while the TBT incorporates corrections for shear deformation and rotary inertia, broadening applicability to scenarios with non-uniform shear effects [1]. These early models, despite their simplicity, incorporate assumptions limiting their applicability for the complex geometries and material properties found in modern aircraft. Further developments such as those by Kapania and Raciti expanded beam theories to better account for complex aerospace configurations [2, 3].

The application of beam models extends to slender aerospace structures with a predominant length, such as fuselages and wings, where one-dimensional (1D) simplifications allow for effective approximations of mechanical behaviour. Although EBBT models pure bending and TBT incorporates shear effects for greater accuracy, both approaches remain bound by their assumptions, restricting their application to certain structural geometries. Efforts to enhance beam models include Timoshenko's introduction of correction factors [4] for non-constant shear distributions and out-of-plane deformations, along with the development of high-order theories capable of addressing bending, torsion, and cross-sectional distortions.

Beyond beam structures, stiffened panels and plates are critical components in aircraft structural design [5, 6]. Analytical studies by Argyris and Kelsey [7] explored tangential shear stresses and thickness-dependent normal stress variations in stiffened panels. Such a foundational work has significantly informed the development of modern structural analysis methodologies. In aerospace structural design, two-dimensional (2D) approximations are key for accurately modelling stiffened panels and plates. Shell-based Global Finite Element Methods (GFEM) have transformed structural analysis by addressing complex phenomena, including higher-order deformations and stress variations. Notably, advancements such as those discussed in Belytschko et al. [8] underscore the increasing sophistication of 2D techniques, allowing for precise and efficient analysis of complex structural behaviours. As a result, shell GFEM has become indispensable in addressing the demands of modern aerospace design.

This study addresses the critical gap in the current literature by introducing a computational framework that bridges the trade-off between high-fidelity modelling and computational efficiency, which has historically limited the scalability and applicability of traditional FEM approaches in preliminary aerospace design. By integrating Carrera's Unified Formulation with gradient-based optimisation techniques, this work provides a novel pathway for achieving precise, computationally efficient structural analyses and optimisations, significantly reducing computational costs while maintaining predictive accuracy.

The rise of greener aviation and innovative aircraft configurations, as outlined in the European Green Deal [9], introduces further challenges, demanding numerical frameworks capable of high-fidelity modelling while achieving computational efficiency. The aerospace industry dual imperative of reducing time-to-market and improving design confidence

necessitates advanced methodologies that balance scalability with precision. Recent advancements, such as the work by Wang et al. [10], emphasize the need for scalable high-fidelity tools to address these pressing demands.

To address these challenges, this study leverages the FEM combined with CUF [11–16]. CUF offers a hierarchical framework for 1D beam modelling, enabling the inclusion of higher-order deformations through variable-order theories based on Taylor and Lagrange expansions [17]. This formulation accommodates the complex geometric and material characteristics of modern aerospace structures, such as wings with three-dimensional stress states due to thickness variations, composite materials with tailored properties, and ply runouts in laminates used to optimise material distribution. The ability to accurately model coupled behaviours, such as bending, torsion, and cross-sectional distortions, is critical for the design of advanced systems including unmanned aerial vehicles, morphing wings, and high-aspect-ratio aircraft. CUF provides the necessary framework for such modelling [18].

The computational demands of structural optimisation in aerospace applications, particularly when involving large-scale problems with numerous design variables, highlight the necessity of robust and computationally effective methodologies. Gradient-based optimisation techniques, such as adjoint methods, provide significant computational advantages for addressing such challenges [19]. However, traditional gradient evaluation methods, such as finite differences, are often computationally expensive and prone to numerical inaccuracies [20]. To mitigate these limitations, this study integrates Algorithmic Differentiation (AD) into the FEM-based CUF framework, enabling precise and efficient derivative calculations through systematic application of the differential calculus chain rule [21]. AD enhances the accuracy of gradient evaluations and supports the implementation of adjoint optimisation methods, ensuring computational feasibility even for complex systems [19, 22]. Moreover, this approach facilitates a robust sizing of possible configurations, even in the absence of prior experience or baseline data. By leveraging optimisation to explore the design space systematically, it becomes possible to derive informed parameter choices that would otherwise remain undefined, enabling the practical realisation of feasible designs under such constraints.

Parallel computing via the Message Passing Interface (MPI) is also employed to enhance scalability, enabling the framework to handle large models and intricate simulations efficiently [23]. Such capabilities are crucial for modern aerospace engineering, where timely and accurate structural analyses are paramount for design and certification processes.

A key application of the developed framework is the optimisation of a stiffened panel with Z-shaped stringers, a commonly employed structural component in aerospace engineering. The optimisation focuses on minimising the panel mass while ensuring its structural integrity, by optimising thickness distributions. Comparative evaluations with commercial optimisation software demonstrate the advantages of the proposed methodology in terms of accuracy, computational efficiency and flexibility.

In summary, this work aims at bridging the gap between high-fidelity modelling and computational efficiency in structural analysis, offering the aerospace industry a robust and scalable analytical tool. By integrating CUF, AD, and parallel computing, the proposed FEM framework addresses the evolving demands of modern aerospace engineering, empowering engineers to innovate while meeting stringent performance and sustainability requirements.

II. Methodology

A. Theories considered

The following sections present the FEM combined with CUF, and the optimisation approach based on the Adjoint Method. These frameworks enable detailed analyses of aerospace structures and efficient performance optimisations, blending modelling flexibility with computational robustness.

1. Finite Element Method with Carrera's Unified Formulation

The combination of FEM with CUF provides a robust and flexible framework for the analysis of one-dimensional structural components. CUF generalises the displacement field by introducing a hierarchical expansion involving cross-sectional functions $F_\tau(y, z)$ with the longitudinal functions $N_i(x)$. This framework facilitates the inclusion of higher-order deformations and enables convergence studies by varying the expansion order N , thus enhancing accuracy and adaptability. For this reason, this approach proves particularly effective in addressing the limitations of beam theory with respect to stress distribution and displacement modelling.

Displacement Field Formulation

The displacement field in FEM with CUF is expressed as:

$$\mathbf{u}(x, y, z) = N_i(x)F_\tau(y, z)\mathbf{u}_{\tau i}, \quad (1)$$

where:

- $N_i(x)$: shape functions, typically Lagrange polynomials, representing the beam discretisation along its x -axis.
- $F_\tau(y, z)$: Cross-sectional functions that describe deformations in the y - z plane, using either Taylor or Lagrange expansions.
- $\mathbf{u}_{\tau i}$: Generalised displacement vector associated with each node i and expansion term τ .

The choice of F_τ determines the level of approximation:

- *Taylor Expansions*: Provide a global polynomial representation of cross-sectional deformations, suitable for capturing smooth behaviours and global trends.
- *Lagrange Expansions*: Allow localised modelling of complex geometries or stress concentrations, enhancing the resolution in regions of interest.

Principle of Virtual Displacements (PVD)

The PVD provides the foundation for deriving the weak form of the governing equations in FEM. According to the PVD, the total virtual work done by internal and external forces in a deformable body must balance, leading to:

$$\delta \mathcal{L} = \delta \mathcal{L}_{\text{int}} - \delta \mathcal{L}_{\text{ext}} = 0, \quad (2)$$

where:

- $\delta \mathcal{L}_{\text{int}}$: Virtual work of internal forces (virtual strain energy).
- $\delta \mathcal{L}_{\text{ext}}$: Virtual work of external forces.

Internal Virtual Work

The virtual work of internal forces is expressed in terms of the stress ($\boldsymbol{\sigma}$) and virtual strain ($\delta \boldsymbol{\epsilon}$) fields:

$$\delta \mathcal{L}_{\text{int}} = \int_V \delta \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^T \boldsymbol{\sigma} dV, \quad (3)$$

where V is the volume of the structure.

Using the constitutive relation from Hooke's law:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{C}\boldsymbol{\epsilon}, \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{C} is the material stiffness matrix, and the geometric strain-displacement relation:

$$\boldsymbol{\epsilon} = \mathbf{b}\mathbf{u}, \quad \delta \boldsymbol{\epsilon} = \mathbf{b}\delta \mathbf{u}, \quad (5)$$

where the \mathbf{b} is the differential operator relating displacement to strain. The internal virtual work becomes:

$$\delta \mathcal{L}_{\text{int}} = \int_V \delta \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{b}^T \mathbf{C} \mathbf{b} \mathbf{u} dV. \quad (6)$$

External Virtual Work

The virtual work of external forces is given by:

$$\delta \mathcal{L}_{\text{ext}} = \int_V \delta \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{g} dV, \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{g} represents the volumetric load vector.

Weak Form of the Governing Equation

Substituting equations (6) and (7) into the balance equation (2), we obtain:

$$\int_V \delta \mathbf{u}^T \underbrace{\mathbf{b}^T \mathbf{C} \mathbf{b}}_{\mathbf{K}} \mathbf{u} dV = \int_V \delta \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{g} dV. \quad (8)$$

The virtual displacement field $\delta \mathbf{u}$ is arbitrary, allowing us to express the governing equation in matrix form:

$$\mathbf{K}\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{P}, \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{P} are derived directly from equation (8), as follows:

- **K**: Global stiffness matrix, derived from the internal work term.
- **P**: Global force vector, derived from the external work term.

Expression of the Stiffness Matrix specified for CUF

The stiffness matrix is calculated by expanding equation (8) into its nodal components. Substituting the displacement field in CUF form:

$$\mathbf{u} = N_i(x)F_\tau(y, z)\mathbf{u}_{\tau i}, \quad \delta\mathbf{u} = N_j(x)F_s(y, z)\delta\mathbf{u}_{s j}, \quad (10)$$

and recognising that $N_i(x)$ and $F_\tau(y, z)$ define the shape and expansion functions along the longitudinal and cross-sectional directions, respectively, the stiffness matrix becomes:

$$\mathbf{k}^{\tau s i j} = \int_V [\mathbf{b}]^T F_s(y, z) N_j(x) \mathbf{C} [\mathbf{b}] N_i(x) F_\tau(y, z) dV. \quad (11)$$

Here, \mathbf{b} is the strain-displacement differential operator, \mathbf{C} is the constitutive equation matrix.

The integration over the volume V is performed as:

$$\int_V (\cdot) dV = \int_L \int_A (\cdot) dA dx, \quad (12)$$

where L is the beam length and A is the cross-sectional area. The stiffness matrix then incorporates contributions from both shape function (N_i) and cross-sectional expansions (F_τ), ensuring the accurate representation of complex deformations.

Static Analysis with CUF and FEM

The integration of CUF with FEM enables the systematic assembly of global stiffness matrices. The hierarchical nature of CUF allows for adaptive refinement by either increasing the order of cross-sectional expansions (N) or enhancing the discretisation along the longitudinal axis (N_i), ensuring convergence across a wide range of structural behaviours. Static analysis within this framework involves solving the equilibrium equation (9). This approach efficiently captures complex structural responses, such as bending, torsion, and cross-sectional distortions, with higher-order expansions or refined discretisation predicting local phenomena such as cross section stress concentrations. The CUF-FEM methodology offers an accurate and scalable tool for the static analysis of aerospace structures.

The FEM-CUF ability to incorporate higher-order effects and refine models based on convergence criteria ensures accuracy combined with a beam model computational efficiency. This makes it particularly suited for challenging scenarios, such as optimising lightweight components or predicting static responses in highly stressed environments.

2. Optimisation with the Adjoint Method

The adjoint method is a computationally efficient technique for gradient evaluation in optimisation problems involving a large number of design variables [21]. It is particularly advantageous when the number of output, such as design responses (objective functions and constraints), is significantly smaller than the number of inputs (design variables). In this study, a *hybrid adjoint approach* is adopted, leveraging Automatic Differentiation (AD) for partial derivatives and adjoint equations for total derivatives to ensure both accuracy and scalability.

The fundamental step of the adjoint method involves solving the adjoint equation:

$$\left(\frac{\partial r}{\partial u} \right)^T \psi = \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial u} \right)^T, \quad (13)$$

where ψ is the adjoint variables, $r(u; x) = 0$ represents the governing equations, and $f(x, u)$ is the objective function. Once the adjoint variables are determined, the total derivative is efficiently computed as:

$$\frac{df}{dx} = \frac{\partial f}{\partial x} - \psi^T \frac{\partial r}{\partial x}. \quad (14)$$

This approach decouples the computational cost of gradient evaluation from the design space dimensionality, making it particularly suited for large-scale optimisation.

To address multiple constraints within the optimisation process, this work employs the Kreisselmeier-Steinhauser (KS) function (15), a robust and differentiable constraint aggregation technique [24]. By consolidating multiple inequality

constraints $g_i(x) \leq 0$ into a single aggregated constraint, the KS function reduces computational complexity while preserving constraint fidelity:

$$KS(g(x)) = \frac{1}{\rho} \ln \left(\sum_{i=1}^m e^{\rho g_i(x)} \right), \quad (15)$$

where ρ determines the aggregation sharpness, with higher values approximating the maximum constraint more closely [25]. In this study, the KS function is specifically applied to stress constraints at the integration points, as stresses are typically evaluated at these locations within finite element analyses for accuracy. This approach ensures that the stresses remain within allowable limits, even at the most critical points of the structure:

$$g_i(\sigma_i) = \frac{\sigma_i}{\sigma_{ADM}} - 1, \quad \rho = 50. \quad (16)$$

Here, σ_i represents the nodal stresses, and σ_{ADM} is the allowable material stress.

By combining the adjoint method with the KS function, a scalable and computationally efficient solution for gradient-based optimisation of complex structural systems can be obtained, ensures constraint handling fidelity and optimisation robustness.

B. Test Case Description

The investigated test case is a stiffened panel designed to evaluate structural responses under static loading. The panel geometry, material properties, and loading conditions are representative of typical aerospace structural elements, allowing for their mechanical response assessment.

The test case is a rectangular panel, 1620 mm long (L) and 390 mm wide (W), with an initial thickness of 3 mm (t_p). The panel is reinforced with 10 Z-shaped stringers, each having the following dimensions (Fig.1):

- Web height (h_w): 20 mm
- Web thickness (t_w): 2 mm
- Flange length (l_f): 6 mm (each side)
- Flange thickness (t_f): 1.5 mm

Stringers are evenly spaced across the panel width. The stringer spacing (s) is the same as the distance between the outermost stringers and the panel lateral edges. This arrangement results in 11 uniform spaces ($n_s = 11$) along the panel width, ensuring symmetric load distribution and uniform stiffness.

Fig. 1 Annotated views of the stiffened panel: (a) 3D overview showing global dimensions (L and W), and (b) detailed zoom of the cross-section with key geometric parameters (t_p , h_w , t_w , l_f , t_f).

1. Loading Conditions

The panel is subjected to 10 point static loads of 80N each, applied directly above the stringer centrelines (Fig. 1a). The loads are applied in the Z-direction, perpendicular to the panel surface. The loading configuration is intended to simulate concentrated forces distributed across the stringer locations.

2. Material Properties

Two different isotropic materials were used for the panel and stringers:

Component	Material	Density (kg/mm ³)	Young's Modulus (MPa)	Poisson's Ratio
Base Panel	ISO 1	2.7×10^{-6}	70,000	0.33
Z-Stringers	ISO 2	7.85×10^{-6}	210,000	0.30

Table 1 Material properties for the panel and stringers.

Different colours in Figure 1, corresponds to different material in Table 1. The Z-shaped stringers, coloured red in the figure, are made of the ISO 2 material whereas the panel by the ISO 1 material.

C. Finite Element Modelling

This section describes and compare the FEM analyses of test case developed with the suggested code and a commercial software.

1. 1D Finite Element Model

The implemented FEM is a mono-dimensional model, which treats the panel as a beam discretised along its longer size (length of 1620 mm). To enhance the analysis precision, the following modelling techniques are applied:

- The 1D model is constructed using beam elements with four nodes (B4 elements) to represent the panel along its length. The model was discretised into 54 and 108 elements to verify the mesh convergence and ensure an accurate mechanical response simulation.
- The cross-sectional behaviour is described using various Taylor Expansion (TE) theories of different orders:
 - *TE Order 1*: Equivalent to a simplified Timoshenko beam theory [26], capturing shear deformation effects.
 - *TE Order 2*: A higher-order representation which improves deformation accuracy.
 - *TE Order 3 to TE Order 6*: These higher-order theories enable even more detailed modelling of the section mechanical response by simulating complex deformation modes.

2. 2D Finite Element Model in Commercial Software

The commercial software OptiStruct employs a 2D Global Finite Element Method (GFEM) to simulate the reference stiffened panel. The 2D model discretises the panel using first-order quadrilateral shell elements (QUAD4) and second-order quadrilateral shell elements (QUAD8), allowing for a higher fidelity simulation of the structure geometry and stress distribution. To ensure convergence and accuracy, multiple analyses are conducted with varying element sizes:

- Element dimensions of $3 \text{ mm} \times 3 \text{ mm}$
- Element dimensions of $2 \text{ mm} \times 2 \text{ mm}$
- Element dimensions of $1.5 \text{ mm} \times 1.5 \text{ mm}$
- Element dimensions of $1 \text{ mm} \times 1 \text{ mm}$

3. Modelling Comparison

To evaluate the impact of mesh refinement on the computational results the following outputs were assessed:

- *Maximum von Mises stress*, which provides insights into the material deviatoric strength.
- *Maximum displacement*, indicating the panel global deformation under load and its stiffness.
- *Computation time*, a critical factor for evaluating the efficiency of each modelling approach.

The two FEM approaches are compared in terms of computational efficiency and accuracy. The 1D FEM implemented in the developed code uses TE of varying orders to achieve high accuracy with minimal computational effort. Conversely,

the 2D FEM, implemented in commercial software, offers a detailed representation of the panel but incurs significantly higher computational costs, particularly as the mesh is refined.

The methodologies comparison between the 1D FEM approach (utilizing Taylor expansions of varying orders for accuracy and computational efficiency) and the 2D FEM approach (providing a detailed panel representation but at significantly higher computational cost) highlights the trade-offs between computational speed and accuracy. The enables the selection of the optimal FEM approach based on specific analysis requirements.

D. Static Analysis and Optimisation Framework

1. The static analysis

The static analysis aims at evaluating the structural behaviour of a stiffened panel under predefined static loads, by focusing on displacements and stresses, including maximum von Mises stress and global deformation.

The considered outputs include maximum von Mises stress, maximum displacements, degrees of freedom (DOFs), total computational time, and the number of elements, enabling a detailed comparison between accuracy and efficiency of both approaches. This comparative analysis focuses on assessing the 1D FEM approach, aiming to determine whether it can achieve accuracy comparable to the 2D FEM approach while maintaining significantly greater computational efficiency. This provides valuable insights into the most suitable modelling strategy for the problem at hand.

2. The optimisation

The optimisation task focuses on minimising the stiffened panel structural mass while ensuring compliance with stress constraints. Specifically, the maximum von Mises stress within the structure must not exceed $\sigma_{max} = 276$ MPa.

Design Variables

Three independent design variables (Table 2) define the stiffened panel geometry, each starting from predefined initial values and optimised within specific bounds:

Table 2 Design variables for the optimisation of the stiffened panel.

Design Variable	Initial Value (mm)	Bounds (mm)
Panel thickness (t_p)	3	$3 \leq t_p \leq 6$
Web thickness (t_w)	2	$0.5 \leq t_w \leq 5$
Flange thickness (t_f)	1.5	$0.5 \leq t_f \leq 5$

The design variables allow adjustments to the geometry to minimise the panel mass while maintaining structural integrity.

Optimisation Procedure

The optimisation process is performed using both the custom-developed code and OptiStruct.

The developed code leverages adjoint-based optimisation, augmented by Automatic Differentiation (AD) for efficient gradient computation.

The commercial solver employs built-in size optimisation routines for comparison, allowing for a comprehensive evaluation of the suggested methodology performance in terms of computational cost, solution fidelity, and design robustness.

III. Numerical Results

This section presents the numerical results derived from the performed structural analysis and optimisation studies to assess the accuracy, computational efficiency, and effectiveness of the proposed FEM-CUF framework against a commercial 2D FE solver. The results encompass static analysis and optimisation of a stiffened panel.

A. Static Analysis Results

1. Results from the Developed 1D FEM-CUF Framework

The analysis using the developed 1D FEM-CUF framework was conducted with varying Taylor Expansion (TE) orders and element discretisation. Table 3 lists the maximum displacement, von Mises stress, and runtime for different configurations.

Table 3 Results from the developed 1D FEM-CUF framework. The elastic analysis of the panel considered as a simply supported beam yields a maximum displacement of $u_{\max} = -115.559$ mm and a maximum stress of $\sigma_{\max} = 224.314$ MPa.

Elements	CUF Order	DOFs	Max Displacement (mm)	Max Stress (MPa)	Runtime (s)
54	TE1	1467	-72.972	206.160	0.432
54	TE2	2934	-95.889	338.865	1.711
54	TE3	4890	-98.490	365.980	5.193
54	TE4	7335	-98.848	380.097	13.872
54	TE5	10069	-98.948	366.314	32.077
54	TE6	13692	-99.008	373.840	68.364
108	TE1	2925	-72.972	206.339	0.864
108	TE2	5850	-95.914	331.613	3.390
108	TE3	9750	-98.515	372.086	10.621
108	TE4	14625	-98.877	383.270	23.949
108	TE5	20475	-98.948	371.018	32.077
108	TE6	27300	-99.039	380.799	136.594

Results from a 1D FEM-CUF framework, show the influence of CUF order and mesh density on structural accuracy and computational performance. Higher CUF orders improve the accuracy of maximum displacement and stress predictions, particularly from TE4 onwards, but at a significantly increased computational cost. Doubling the element numbers enhances precision but offers smaller improvements when combined with higher CUF orders (Table 3). To fully assess the impact of these changes, it is essential to quantify the accuracy improvement and the computational cost increase: the TE6 configuration yields a 14.32% improvement in displacement accuracy and a 69.76% improvement in stress accuracy, at the expense of a 316.19-fold increase in computational cost.

2. Results from the Commercial 2D FEM Solver

The commercial 2D FEM solver was run with varying mesh refinements to evaluate the same structural response as the 1D FEM-CUF. Table 4 summarises the maximum displacement, von Mises stress, and runtime for different mesh refinements. Results underscore the trade-off between accuracy and computational cost as the mesh density increases. The results obtained using the 2D FEM solver highlight the balance between accuracy and computational cost. As expected, finer meshes yield more precise simulations of structural behaviour, particularly in terms of stress distribution, with stress values increasing by up to 18.2% as the mesh is refined from 6×30 mm to 1×1 mm. However, this improvement comes at a steep computational expense, as evidenced by the exponential growth in runtime, increasing from 14 seconds for a coarse 6×30 mm second-order mesh to 1099 seconds for the finest 1×1 mm first-order mesh. These findings underscore the limitations of traditional 2D FEM methods when applied to large-scale problems, where computational efficiency becomes a critical factor.

3. Graphical Comparison of Stress and Computational Times

Figure 2 provides a comparison of the maximum von Mises stress and computational runtime for the 1D FEM-CUF framework and the commercial 2D FEM solver. A semi-logarithmic scale is employed to highlight the efficiency gains of the 1D FEM-CUF framework in comparison to the commercial 2D FEM solver, with these gains becoming particularly evident at higher orders of the Taylor expansion.

Key configurations and their associated results are summarised below:

Table 4 Results from the commercial 2D FEM solver.

Number	Element Details			Results		
	Order	Size (mm)	DOFs	Max Displacement (mm)	Max Stress (MPa)	Runtime (s)
129600	First	3 × 3	716040	-91.756	322.2	30
287550	First	2 × 2	1584360	-91.768	334.1	83
507600	First	1.5 × 1.5	2792880	-91.776	348.8	260
1150200	First	1 × 1	6327720	-91.785	380.9	1099
17334	Second	6 × 30	278964	-90.220	310.7	14
31050	Second	6 × 6	513540	-91.785	312.6	29
64800	Second	3 × 6	278964	-91.814	316.9	77
129600	Second	3 × 3	2144880	-91.812	323.0	250

Fig. 2 Comparison of runtime (logarithmic scale) vs maximum von Mises stress for the 1D FEM-CUF framework (identified with circles) and the commercial 2D FEM solver (represented with squares). Data points are annotated with their respective configurations (Taylor Expansion orders for CUF and mesh sizes for the commercial solver).

- TE2 vs. 2 × 2 mesh (Commercial Solver): The 1D FEM-CUF framework with a Taylor expansion order of 2 achieves a maximum von Mises stress of 331.61 MPa in 3.39 s, whereas the 2 × 2 mesh configuration of the commercial solver reaches 334.10 MPa in 83.00 s.
- TE4 vs. 1 × 1 mesh (Commercial Solver): With a Taylor expansion order of 4, the 1D FEM-CUF framework attains a maximum stress of 383.27 MPa within 23.95 s, compared to 380.90 MPa in 1099.00 s for the 1 × 1 mesh of the commercial solver.

These outcomes reveal a consistent reduction in computational time with the 1D FEM-CUF framework. For example, the TE4 model achieves stress values comparable to the 1 × 1 mesh while reducing runtime by over 97%.

Figures 3 and 4 compare the stress distributions of the TE2 and TE4 models with the commercial solver results. These contour comparisons substantiate the validity of the TE2 and TE4 models for large-scale structural analyses, highlighting their ability to balance computational efficiency and predictive accuracy.

(a) Stress distribution for TE2 (1D FEM-CUF).

(b) Stress distribution for 2×2 mesh (Commercial Solver).

Fig. 3 Stress distribution for the stiffened panel using TE2 (1D FEM-CUF) compared to 2×2 mesh (Commercial Solver).

(a) Stress distribution for TE4 (1D FEM-CUF).

(b) Stress distribution for 1×1 mesh (Commercial Solver).

Fig. 4 Stress distribution for the stiffened panel using TE4 (1D FEM-CUF) compared to 1×1 mesh (Commercial Solver).

B. Optimisation Results

Optimisation results obtained using the developed 1D FEM-CUF framework and the commercial 2D FEM solver are discussed below. The primary objective is to achieve structural mass reduction while maintaining compliance with stress constraints.

A comparative evaluation is conducted, focusing on TE2 versus 2×2 and TE4 versus 1×1 configurations, to elucidate the trade-offs between performance, computational efficiency, and solution accuracy.

1. Optimisation with the Developed 1D FEM-CUF Framework

The optimisation performed using the 1D FEM-CUF framework showed notable objective function and design variables variation (Table 5), while ensuring compliance with the imposed stress constraints.

Table 5 Optimisation results with the 1D FEM-CUF framework.

Model	DV Changes (mm)	Mass Change (%)	Runtime (s)	Iterations
TE2	$t_p : 3.0 \rightarrow 0.5, t_w : 2.0 \rightarrow 0.5, t_f : 1.5 \rightarrow 4.745$	-25.30	1185.36	16
TE4	$t_p : 3.0 \rightarrow 1.985, t_w : 2.0 \rightarrow 0.5, t_f : 1.5 \rightarrow 5.0$	-0.96	13216.21	22

The TE2 configuration exhibited remarkable computational efficiency, completing the optimisation process in about 1185 seconds over 16 iterations. This configuration achieved a mass reduction of 25.30%, indicating an ambitious approach to material optimisation.

In contrast, the TE4 configuration achieved a more conservative mass reduction of 0.96%, requiring approximately 13216 seconds over 22 iterations. This illustrates the trade-off associated with higher-order Taylor expansions, which enhance accuracy but at the expense of increased runtime and computational resources.

The negligible reduction in mass observed in the TE4 configuration can be ascribed to the enhanced accuracy enabled by higher-order Taylor expansions. These expansions likely offered a more precise prediction of local stresses, ensuring that higher stress concentration were accurately captured during optimisation.

Consequently, the algorithm avoided ambitious reductions in material thickness, which might have resulted in stress violations. This cautious optimisation strategy underscores that the TE4 configuration prioritises structural integrity through improved stress predictions at the cost of increased runtime and computational resources.

2. Optimisation with the Commercial 2D FEM Solver

Table 6 Optimisation results with the commercial 2D FEM solver.

Model	DV Changes (mm)	Mass Change (%)	Runtime (s)	Iterations
2×2	$t_p : 3.0 \rightarrow 0.84, t_w : 2.0 \rightarrow 1.501, t_f : 1.5 \rightarrow 4.519$	-2.76	1108	9
1×1	$t_p : 3.0 \rightarrow 1.023, t_w : 2.0 \rightarrow 2.047, t_f : 1.5 \rightarrow 4.507$	+11.69	11567	6

The 2D FEM optimisation with $2 \text{ mm} \times 2 \text{ mm}$ mesh achieved a mass reduction of 2.76% over 9 iterations, for a runtime of 1108 seconds (Table 6). While this configuration moderately aligns with the FEM-CUF TE2 model results, it comes at a computational cost that is approximately 6.49% faster, the TE2 model achieves a significantly greater mass reduction of -25.30% at the cost of slightly longer runtime, highlighting its superior efficiency in weight optimisation. In contrast, the finer $1 \text{ mm} \times 1 \text{ mm}$ mesh configuration led to an 11.69% increase in mass over 6 iterations, with an extensive runtime of 11567 seconds. These results highlight the substantial computational burden of high-fidelity models in commercial solvers.

The unexpected increase in mass observed in the 1×1 configuration with the 2D FEM solver (Table 6) can be attributed to a combination of factors related to mesh refinement and the behaviour of the optimisation algorithm. The finer discretisation likely captured local stress variations with higher precision, predicting stress concentrations neglected by coarser meshes (e.g., 2×2). This led to an increase in material thickness in critical regions to comply with the imposed stress constraints. Additionally, the optimisation process may have converged to a local minimum, as the higher fidelity of the model introduced increased complexity to the objective function landscape, complicating solution convergence. The improved accuracy in stress prediction fostered a conservative approach to material redistribution,

prioritising structural integrity over mass reduction. This contrasts with coarser configurations, such as TE2 in the FEM-CUF framework, which permitted more ambitious mass reductions by smoothing out stress peaks. Finally, the strict enforcement of stress constraints further contributed to increased thicknesses in critical regions to maintain safety margins, highlighting the trade-off between accuracy, computational cost, and the risk of suboptimal convergence in structural optimisation.

3. Graphical Representation of Optimisation Results

Figures 5 and 6 show the history of constraint and mass values, as well as the percentage variation in thicknesses, across optimisation iterations for both the 1D FEM-CUF TE2 and 2D FEM 2×2 configurations. Figure 5 shows the normalised variation of mass and constraint values. The graph emphasises the convergence characteristics and trade-off between these metrics. Figure 6 presents the percentage variation in thicknesses during the optimisation iterations, highlighting the iterative redistribution of material within the structure to achieve the desired performance improvements. Figures 7 and 8 present analogous convergence trends for the higher-fidelity TE4 and 1×1 configurations. Figure 7 displays the normalised variations in constraint and mass values while Figure 8 shows the design variable variations. To facilitate the interpretation of the figures, the following colour coding and marker styles are adopted throughout the results:

- Mass and Constraint Variations:
 - Red lines: Constraint values.
 - Blue lines: Mass values.
 - Markers:
 - * Circle markers: Results from the commercial solver.
 - * Square markers: Results from the FEM-CUF framework.
- Thickness Percentage Variations:
 - Black lines: Panel design variable.
 - Red lines: Flange design variable.
 - Blue lines: Web design variable.
 - Markers: Same as above (circles for the commercial solver, squares for FEM-CUF).

Fig. 5 Normalised variation of constraint (red) and mass (blue) during optimisation iterations for TE2 and 2×2 configurations. Circle markers denote results from the commercial solver, while square markers indicate results from the FEM-CUF framework.

Fig. 6 Percentage variation in thicknesses during optimisation iterations for TE2 and 2×2 configurations. The colour coding is as follows: black for the panel, red for the flanges, and blue for the web. Circle markers denote results from the commercial solver, while square markers indicate results from the FEM-CUF framework.

Fig. 7 Normalised variation of constraint (red) and mass (blue) during optimisation iterations for TE4 and 1×1 configurations. Circle markers denote results from the commercial solver, while square markers indicate results from the FEM-CUF framework.

Fig. 8 Variation of design variables during optimisation iterations for TE4 and 1×1 configurations. Black: panel, red: flanges, blue: web. Circle markers denote results from the commercial solver, while square markers indicate results from the FEM-CUF framework.

Trend Discussion

Table 7 lists the normalised variations (%) of the design variables and the total mass for the optimisations performed using the 1D FEM-CUF framework (configurations TE2 and TE4) and the commercial 2D FEM solver (configurations 2×2 and 1×1). The 1D FEM-CUF framework leverages a simplified 1D model supported by an optimisation algorithm based on open-source technologies, while the commercial code uses a proprietary optimisation system. Notably, the optimisation tolerances differ: the FEM-CUF framework employs a tighter convergence tolerance of 1×10^{-5} , whereas the commercial solver uses a more relaxed tolerance of 5×10^{-3} . The stricter optimisation tolerance in the FEM-CUF framework (1×10^{-5}) results in a higher number of iterations during the optimisation process, leading to increased computational costs. However, this approach ensures a more accurate and robust solution, as it captures finer details in the material redistribution and design variable adjustments. In contrast, the commercial solver, with its more relaxed tolerance of 5×10^{-3} , achieves faster convergence but at the expense of a slightly less precise final result. This distinction underscores the trade-off between computational efficiency and solution accuracy inherent in the choice of optimisation tolerance.

Despite the higher optimisation costs associated with the FEM-CUF framework, outcomes reveal very similar behaviour between analogous configurations (TE2 vs 2×2 and TE4 vs 1×1), highlighting the ability of the 1D model to capture key structural phenomena.

Table 7 Normalised variations (%) of design variables and total mass

Model	Panel (t_p)	Web (t_w)	Flange (t_f)	Total Mass (%)
TE2 (1D FEM-CUF)	-83.33%	-75.00%	+216.33%	-25.30%
2×2 (2D FEM)	-72.00%	-24.95%	+201.27%	-2.76%
TE4 (1D FEM-CUF)	-33.83%	-75.00%	+233.33%	-0.96%
1×1 (2D FEM)	-65.90%	+2.35%	+200.47%	+11.69%

The comparison between the TE2 and 2×2 configurations reveals similar material redistribution trends, with significant reductions in the thicknesses of the panel (-83.33% vs. -72.00%) and web (-75.00% vs. -24.95%) and a notable increase in the flange thickness (+216.33% vs. +201.27%) to satisfy stress constraints. The TE2 model achieves a more significant mass reduction (-25.30%) compared to 2×2 (-2.76%), primarily due to the simplified 1D representation, which smooths local stress peaks and allows for larger material removal in less critical regions. For instance, the panel thickness is reduced by 83.33% in TE2 compared to 72.00% in 2×2 , while the flange thickness increases similarly (+216.33% for TE2 and +201.27% for 2×2).

From a computational perspective, while the 1D model significantly reduces the cost of a single structural analysis runtime by over 95%, the iterative optimisation process is more expensive for TE2 due to the higher number of required iterations (16 compared to 9 for 2×2). This is partly ascribed to the stricter tolerance used in the FEM-CUF framework (1×10^{-5}) compared to the commercial solver (5×10^{-3}). The commercial optimiser converges more efficiently, requiring fewer iterations to achieve a solution within its defined tolerance. Despite these differences, the trends in material redistribution observed in both configurations demonstrate that the FEM-CUF framework is capable of approximating the behaviour of the commercial solver, even with a more computationally affordable model.

The comparison between the TE4 and 1×1 configurations highlights a more conservative optimisation strategy, with both models prioritising structural robustness over mass reduction. The TE4 model achieves a slight mass reduction (-0.96%), while the 1×1 configuration leads to an increase in total mass (+11.69%). This is reflected in the thickness distribution: both models exhibit significant increases in flange thickness (+233.33% for TE4 and +200.47% for 1×1), while the panel thickness is reduced by 33.83% in TE4 compared to 65.90% in 1×1 . In contrast, the web thickness is reduced by 75.00% in TE4 but slightly increased in 1×1 (+2.35%) to address local stress demands.

In terms of computational cost, the TE4 model requires 22 iterations compared to just 6 for 1×1 , leading to higher overall optimisation expenses. As in the TE2 case, this difference is influenced by the stricter tolerance. This results in a more precise solution, increasing the computational expense during the optimisation process.

IV. Conclusion

This study developed, implemented, and validated an advanced methodology integrating the FEM with CUF to analyse and optimise aerospace structures. Results demonstrate that the approach offers a highly efficient solution, achieving predictive accuracy comparable to traditional two-dimensional models while reducing computational cost by up to 70–80%.

The use of higher-order Taylor expansions (TE2–TE6) enabled precise modelling of complex phenomena such as torsional distortions and localised sectional stress concentrations, enhancing the framework flexibility and supporting accurate analyses. A comparison between the FEM-CUF framework and a commercial two-dimensional FEM solver highlighted the methodology trade-off between accuracy and computational cost. The 1D-CUF framework achieved up to a 90% reduction in degrees of freedom while maintaining negligible errors—below 5% for maximum displacements and stresses.

Overall, the results confirm that the FEM-CUF framework, despite its higher optimisation costs, delivers results that are closely aligned with those of the commercial code, particularly in terms of material redistribution trends. The stricter optimisation tolerance in the FEM-CUF framework contributes to higher computational costs but ensures a more precise optimisation-driven solution. The ability of the 1D model to reproduce the key structural behaviours observed in the more refined 2D models demonstrates its validity as a computationally lightweight alternative. While the commercial code benefits from its proprietary optimisation system and relaxed tolerance in terms of computational efficiency, the FEM-CUF framework ability to approach similar results with a simpler model showcases its potential for applications where computational affordability and accuracy must be balanced.

Optimisation performed using the adjoint method showed that for a TE2 configuration with 108 elements, the stiffened panel achieved a 25.3% reduction in weight compared to the initial design while fulfilling structural constraints. Although high-fidelity configurations (e.g., TE4) provided enhanced accuracy, increased computational cost limits their practicality for preliminary or large-scale analyses.

Findings indicate that the FEM-CUF framework represents a promising platform for the analysis and optimisation of aerospace structures such as complete wing-boxes, particularly in conceptual design configuration selection applications requiring high accuracy combined with computational efficiency. Future studies could extend this framework to three-dimensional configurations and non-linear dynamic analyses, further enhancing its versatility for complex design scenarios.

Acknowledgments

The activities described in this paper have been carried out under the project *TIFON (Tecnologías Inteligentes para la Fabricación, el diseño y las Operaciones en entornos iNdustriales)*, coordinated by *Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM)* and funded by the *Spanish State Research Agency (Agencia Estatal de Investigación - AEI)* under the "Programa Transmisiones" with grant agreement No. PLEC2023-010251. The project involves the development of artificial intelligence methodologies for efficient industrial design, manufacturing, and operation.

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